

Data supplement A: Immunohistological assessment of Tyrosine Hydroxylase (TH) expression by intestinal human enterocytes. A survey of the Human Protein Atlas (<https://www.proteinatlas.org/>) allowed extracting immunohistochemical data obtained on human small intestine for the molecule Tyrosine Hydroxylase (*TH*). Scale bar: 25 μm .

Data supplement B: Kinetics of ACE2, SLC6A19, SLC7A9 and SLC6A10 mRNA levels in SARS-CoV2-infected human enterocytes. Data were extracted from a recently published dataset in which RNA-seq analyses were performed on control vs SARS-CoV2 infected human intestinal organoids [34]. RNA-seq values expressed as normalized reads per million (RPM) are shown for *ACE2*, *SLC6A19*, *SLC7A9* and *SLC6A10* under 3 experimental conditions: differentiated human intestinal organoids in control conditions (n = 2), differentiated human intestinal organoids at 24h following infection with SARS-Cov2 (n = 2), differentiated human intestinal organoids at 60h following infection with SARS-Cov2 (n = 2).

Data supplement C: List of the top-25 genes that more closely co-express with ACE2 in SARS-CoV2-infected human enterocytes. A set of previously published RNA-seq data [34] obtained from the analysis of SARS-CoV2-infected human intestinal organoids was re-assessed in order to identify the top-25 genes that more closely co-express with ACE2 under these experimental conditions.

Gene Symbol	Gene Name
<i>ACSL5</i>	acyl-CoA synthetase long-chain family member 5
<i>ALDOB</i>	aldolase B, fructose-bisphosphate
<i>ATP1A1</i>	ATPase, Na ⁺ /K ⁺ transporting, alpha 1 polypeptide
<i>BTD</i>	biotinidase
<i>CENPJ</i>	centromere protein J
<i>CREB3L3</i>	cAMP responsive element binding protein 3-like 3
<i>CYP3A4</i>	cytochrome P450, family 3, subfamily A, polypeptide 4
<i>DMD</i>	dystrophin
<i>GATM</i>	glycine amidinotransferase
<i>GLRX</i>	glutaredoxin
<i>GSTM4</i>	glutathione S-transferase mu 4
<i>IGIP</i>	IgA-inducing protein homolog
<i>MAOB</i>	monoamine oxidase B
<i>MTTP</i>	microsomal triglyceride transfer protein
<i>OAT</i>	ornithine aminotransferase
<i>PCYOX1</i>	prenylcysteine oxidase 1
<i>PDCD4</i>	programmed cell death 4
<i>PHGR1</i>	proline/histidine/glycine-rich 1
<i>PLD1</i>	phospholipase D1
<i>RARRES1</i>	retinoic acid receptor responder
<i>RBP2</i>	retinol binding protein 2
<i>SGK1</i>	serum/glucocorticoid regulated kinase 1
<i>SLC5A1</i>	solute carrier family 5
<i>TMBIM6</i>	transmembrane BAX inhibitor motif containing 6
<i>TTC36</i>	tetratricopeptide repeat domain 36

Data supplement D: Enrichment analysis of the ACE2 co-expression network. An enrichment analysis was performed on the list of top-25 genes that more closely co-express with *ACE2* in SARS-CoV2-infected human enterocytes. To this aim we used the Enrichr platform of enrichment analyses (<https://maayanlab.cloud/Enrichr/>) and queried the BioPlanet library of pathways (created and run by the National Institute of Health, USA) [37], which compiles and integrates libraries of pathways from a large range of sources. The top-10 most significantly enriched pathways, the corresponding adjusted p-values and genes annotated with each pathway are shown below.

Pathway	Adjusted P-value	Genes
Metabolism	1.78E-4	<i>GSTM4, GATM, OAT, BTM, MAOB, MTP, ACSL5, GLRX, ALDOB, CYP3A4, PLD1</i>
Arginine and proline metabolism	0.002	<i>GATM, OAT, MAOB</i>
Drug metabolism: cytochrome P450	0.006	<i>GSTM4, MAOB, CYP3A4</i>
Urea cycle and metabolism of amino groups	0.008	<i>GATM, OAT</i>
mTOR signaling pathway	0.009	<i>PDCD4, PLD1, SGK1</i>
Biological oxidations	0.011	<i>GSTM4, MAOB, CYP3A4</i>
Glycine, serine and threonine metabolism	0.011	<i>GATM, MAOB</i>
Alpha-synuclein signaling	0.011	<i>MAOB, PLD1</i>
Aldosterone-regulated sodium reabsorption	0.017	<i>ATP1A1, SGK1</i>
Tryptophan metabolism	0.029	<i>MAOB, CYP3A4</i>

Data supplement E: Results extracted from metabolomics analyses performed on blood samples from COVID-19 patients. Relevant results from two recently-published metabolomics studies [71, 72] are presented below in E1-E3 (results extracted from Ref [71]) and E4 (results extracted from Ref [72]).

E1: Enrichment analysis from the whole list of metabolites exhibiting altered blood levels in COVID-19 patients as compared to controls [71].

E2: Measures of tryptophan levels (expressed in μM) in the blood of COVID-19 patients as compared to controls [71].

E3: Measures of neutral amino acids (expressed in arbitrary units) as assessed by mass spectrometry in the blood of controls patients (grey circles) vs COVID patients with different blood levels of interleukine-6 (IL-6)(light blue circles = low IL-6 levels ; dark blue circle = medium IL-6 levels ; purple circles = high IL-6 levels) [71].

E4: Extracted results showing statistically significant fold changes in blood levels of relevant metabolites in comparisons of non severe COVID-19 patients vs healthy subjects (1st table) and severe COVID-19 patients vs healthy subjects (2nd table) [72].

Non Severe COVID-19 vs Healthy subjects		
Metabolites	Fold change	Adjusted p-value
asparagine	-0,675798	7,5216E-07
glutamine	-0,294186	0,000990825
glycine	-0,571081	8,06036E-06
isoleucine	-0,613711	1,11056E-05
leucine	-0,510385	5,67243E-06
methionine	-0,713963	3,19159E-08
proline	-0,870753	6,94713E-08
serine	-0,435634	0,000117601
threonine	-0,80806	5,31282E-07
tryptophan	-0,639467	2,40902E-07
tyrosine	-0,323365	0,034459511
valine	-0,550451	1,69336E-07
dopamine 3-O-sulfate	-0,998589	0,001989449

Severe COVID-19 vs Healthy subjects		
glutamine	-0,316643	0,014151896
glycine	-0,580321	0,000207618
isoleucine	-0,79801	1,90408E-05
leucine	-0,533004	0,000523773
methionine	-0,583045	0,000290771
proline	-0,923271	2,51193E-07
serine	-0,409389	0,002062248
threonine	-0,785386	3,41246E-05
tryptophan	-0,567395	0,000284531
valine	-0,548777	0,000206703